

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF VANDHYATVA ASSOCIATED WITH BAD OBSTETRIC HISTORY: A CASE REPORT

*¹Dr. Pratiksha Mane and ²Dr. Anupama V.

¹PG Scholar, Department of Prasuti tantra and Stree roga, Sri Kalabyreshwara Swamy Ayurvedic Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Bengaluru.

²HOD and Professor, Department of Prasuti tantra and Stree Roga, Sri Kalabyreshwara Swamy Ayurvedic Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Bengaluru.

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Pratiksha Mane

PG Scholar, Department of Prasuti tantra and Stree roga, Sri Kalabyreshwara Swamy Ayurvedic Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Bengaluru. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18152097>

How to cite this Article: *¹Dr. Pratiksha Mane and ²Dr. Anupama V. (2026). Ayurvedic Management Of Vandhyatva Associated With Bad Obstetric History: A Case Report. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Science, 12(1), 159–163.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 05/12/2025

Article Revised on 25/12/2025

Article Published on 01/01/2026

ABSTRACT

Infertility is a complex reproductive disorder with multifactorial etiology, affecting a significant proportion of women worldwide. In Ayurveda, infertility is described under Vandhyatva, arising due to vitiation of Doṣhas, particularly Vāta, impairment of Artava, and dysfunction of the Artavavaha srotas. This case report presents the Ayurvedic management of a 29-year-old female suffering from infertility for five years with bad obstetric history, associated with recurrent vaginal infection, positive TORCH IgG markers, menstrual discomfort, psychological stress, and digestive disturbances. Based on Ayurvedic assessment, the condition was diagnosed as Vāta-Kapha pradhāna Tridoṣaja Vandhyatva with Apāna Vāta duṣṭi. The therapeutic approach included Śodhana (Vamana karma) followed by Śamana therapies and Basti karma—namely Anuvāsana Basti, Uttarabasti, and Mātrā Basti—along with internal medications possessing Vātānulomana, and Rasāyana properties. Modern investigations such as follicular studies and hysterosalpingography revealed normal uterine anatomy, indicating functional infertility. Following systematic Ayurvedic intervention, significant improvement was observed in menstrual regularity, vaginal health, psychological wellbeing, and reproductive function, culminating in successful conception and continuation of pregnancy. This case highlights the potential role of Ayurveda as a safe and effective approach in the management of infertility.

KEYWORDS: Infertility, Apāna Vāta, Basti karma, Vamana, TORCH infection.

INTRODUCTION

‘Stree Hi Mulampatyānamstree Hi Rakshatirakshita’ Women indeed is the source of human progeny. When protected, she protects the progeny. Woman undoubtedly is the ultimate source of human progeny. The continuity and health of the society as well as universe depends upon her. Hence prime importance has been laid upon her health care in Indian Shastras due to her role in giving birth to Shreyasipraja - a progeny which is physically, mentally, socially as well as spiritually healthy. ‘Styayate Asyaam Garbhaha Iti Stree’ i.e. a body where Garbha gets impregnated and receives nourishment is called Stree. Garbha is defined as, ‘Shukra Shonita Jeeva Samyoge Tu Khalu Kukshigate

Garbha Sangnaa Bhavati’.^[1] Acharya Sushruta has included some more factors essential in the conjugation i.e. Aatma, Prakruti and Vikaara. Dalhana has commented that Aatma is the Kshetraajna. Factors that are responsible for the formation of Garbha^[2] are: The healthy Shukra and Shonita are two essential components of Garbha. Conjugated Shukra and Shonita rest in the (healthy) Garbha-Aashyaha, Jeeva (Aatma Prakruti Vikaara Sammurchheetam) Avtarana takes place in conjugated Shukra and Shonita.^[3]

Infertility is an emerging global health concern, affecting approximately 10–15% of reproductive-age couples, with female-related factors contributing substantially.

Modern gynecology attributes infertility to ovulatory dysfunction, tubal pathology, uterine abnormalities, endocrine disorders, recurrent genital infections, and unexplained causes. Despite advances in assisted reproductive technologies, many cases remain unresolved due to persistent physiological and psychosomatic disturbances.

In Ayurveda, infertility is described under Vandhyatva, where successful conception depends on the proper functioning of Ritu, Ksetra, Ambu, and Bija. Disturbance in any of these factors—especially due to vitiation of Vāta Doṣa—leads to reproductive failure. Apāna Vāta plays a crucial role in menstruation, ovulation, fertilization, and implantation; its derangement manifests as irregular cycles, dysmenorrhea, implantation failure, or unexplained infertility.

Ayurvedic management focuses on correcting Doṣic imbalance, purifying reproductive channels (Srotoshodhana), nourishing reproductive tissues, and restoring hormonal and psychological balance. Basti karma is considered the most effective therapy for regulating Vāta and improving pelvic organ function. This case report aims to illustrate the effectiveness of a comprehensive Ayurvedic approach in managing primary infertility complicated by recurrent vaginal and TORCH infections, ultimately resulting in conception.

Case Presentation

A 29-year-old married female came to OPD Of Prasuti Tantra & Streeroga at Sri kalabyreshwara swamy ayurvedic medical college, hospital and research Centre, presented with Anxious to conceive for five years with

bad obstetric history. History was taken thoroughly and examined her properly.

Present Medical History

Patient is anxious to conceive. She complained of recurrent vaginal itching with thick white discharge, dysmenorrhea, lower abdominal pain, anxiety, disturbed sleep, and reduced appetite. Menstrual cycles were irregular at times with excessive discharge.

History of Past illness

She had a history of hypothyroidism under regular medication.

Personal History

Married Life – 8 years
Occupation – Housewife
Diet – Mixed (Veg/Non-veg)
Appetite – Good
Bowel – 2 times/day
Micturition – 5-6 times/day
Sleep – Disturbed

Menstrual History

MC – Regular
MH – 2 days/ 28-30 days
Clots + Each day 1-2 Pads/day

Obstetric History

P0L0A3D0
A1 – Ectopic Pregnancy
A2 – Spontaneous at 1½ month
A3 – Spontaneous at 1½ month

Dashvidha Parikshana

Table No 1: Dashvidha Parikshana.

Prakruti – Pitta Pradhan vata	Satmya - Madhyama
Vikruti - Vata	Satva - Pravara
Sara – Madhyama	Ahara shakti – Madhyama
Samhanana – Madhyama	Vyayam Shakti –Madhyama
Pramana - Madhyama	Vaya – Yuva Awastha

Table No 2: General Examination.

General Examination	Systemic Examination
BP – 110/80 mm hg	RS - AEBE
PR - 78/min	CVS - S1 S2 Heard
RR – 22/min	CNS – Conscious, Oriented
Weight – 47 Kg	P/A -Soft Non tender
Nourishment - Poor	P/V – Cx Healthy, Nulliparous OS No Erosion noted White discharge + CMT +

Investigation

Date	Findings
Investigations 24/9/24	Toxoplasma IGG – 23.60 IU/ml Rubella IgG – 73.80 IU/ml Cytomegalovirus IgG – 26.50 IU/ml AMH – 4.30 ng/ml
2/3/25	ESR – 46mm/hr
USG 27/2/2025	Uterus anteverted Normal in size & echo Pattern Right ovarian simple cyst Mild collection in Pouch of Douglas

Intervention

The patient with primary infertility was managed using a stepwise Ayurvedic treatment protocol based on clinical findings and Ayurvedic principles. The intervention included Śodhana, Śamana, and procedural therapies, administered over a defined timeline.

The patient first presented on 24 September 2024. Following clinical evaluation, Śodhana therapy was planned. She underwent Udwartana followed by Snehapana with Phalaghrita and Sr. Abhyanga Mahanarayana taila^[4] and bashpa sweda f/b Vamana Karma. After completion of the procedure, oral Ayurvedic medications were initiated from 6 January 2025, including GP 500 (1–0–1), Torch Free (1–0–1), and Repromed (1–0–1) for 15 days.

After the completion of the subsequent menstrual cycle on 16 February 2025, Basti therapy was administered. This included Anuvāsana Basti with Phalāghṛta for 8 days, followed by Uttar Basti using Phalāghṛta and Kāsīsa Taila^[5] for 3 days, with the aim of improving uterine function and ovarian responsiveness.

On 22 March 2025, the patient reported vulval itching and thick curdy white vaginal discharge with foul odor. Management included external Panchavalkala vaginal wash, Chandraprabhā Vati^[6] (1–1–1), GP 500 (1–0–1), and Candid-B cream for external application for 7 days, resulting in symptomatic relief.

Subsequent follow-ups on 16 April 2025 and 5 May 2025 included investigations such as follicular study and hysterosalpingography (HSG). Supportive medications—Livogen-Z (1–0–1), Torchnil (1–0–1), and Cystolib Nutra (1–0–1)—were prescribed for one month to optimize nutritional status and reproductive function.

At the follow-up visit on 25 June 2025, a repeat follicular study was conducted. Additionally, Mātrā Basti with Phalāghṛta (75 ml) was administered for 7 consecutive days to support endometrial receptivity and facilitate conception.

RESULTS

There were remarkable changes in various symptoms and most importantly Patient Conceived, as shown below.

Date	Treatment	Observation
24/9/25 - 6/1/25	Shodhana – Vamana Karma Snehapana – Phala ghrita Sr. Abhynga with – M.N taila Orally – • Cap. GP 500 1-0-1 • Cap. Torch free 1-0-1 • Cap Repromed 1-0-1	TORCH Markers reduce significantly Menstrual Cycle Flow improved
16/2/25 – 9/4/25	• Anyvasana basti with Phalaghrita 8 days • Uttara basti with Phalaghrita and Kasisa taila 3 days • Panchavalkala drops ext. wash • Chandraprabha vati 1-1-1 • G.P 500 1-0-1 • Candid B Cream for E/A For 7 days	White discharge reduced Vulval itching reduced
16/4/25 – 26/5/25	• Follicular study & HSG • Tab Livogen Z 1-0-1 • Tab Torchnil 1-0-1 • Tab Cystolib Nutra 1-0-1 for 1 month	On HSG revealed Normal Uterine Morphology
25/6/25	• Follicular Study • Matra basti with Phala ghrita 75 ml for 7 days	Patient came with 1 MOA on 21/7/25 LMP – 13/6/25

After 1 month of Treatment

- UPT – Positive
- LMP – 13/6/25
- EDD – 20/3/26
- Early Pregnancy Scan 14/8/25
 - Single live intra uterine gestation 8 weeks 2 days
 - FHR – 168 bpm
 - CRL – 18.3 mm
- She successfully conceived

DISCUSSION

The present case of infertility with a history of recurrent pregnancy loss, TORCH positivity, vaginal infection, hypothyroidism, and psychological stress reflects a complex interplay of systemic and reproductive dysfunctions. From an Ayurvedic standpoint, the condition was assessed as Vāta-Kapha pradhāna Tridoṣaja Vandhyatva with involvement of Artavavaha srotas and Apāna Vāta duṣṭi.

Recurrent vaginal discharge and infection indicate Kapha-pitta involvement with Srotodushti, while anxiety, dysmenorrhea, and disturbed sleep signify Vāta aggravation. Elevated TORCH IgG markers suggest chronic infection and impaired immunity, which can be correlated with Āma and Dhātu-agnimāndya. Normal uterine morphology and ovarian reserve (AMH) point towards functional rather than structural infertility.

The treatment strategy was planned in a phased manner. Vamana karma was administered as Śodhana to eliminate Kapha and Āma, improve metabolic fire, and enhance drug receptivity. Internal medications with antimicrobial, immunomodulatory, and reproductive tonic properties helped in reducing infection and improving general health.

Basti karma played a pivotal role in the management. Anuvāsana Basti and Mātrā Basti with Phalaghrita helped normalize Apāna Vāta, improve follicular maturation, and nourish reproductive tissues. Uttar basti^[7] strengthens and rejuvenates the endometrium by pacifying Vata and clearing the channels of Artavavaha Srotas. It improves the blood circulation of uterus and pelvic organs. Phalaghrita used for Uttar Basti has hormonal modulating properties and prepare the uterus for conception. Significant reduction in vaginal discharge and vulval itching reflects the local cleansing and healing effect of Ayurvedic formulations.

Phala Ghrita^[8] is added for proper revivification of the endometrium. Is a uterine alcohol. It acts on the endometrium and helps to stabilize the growth of it, if it's a poor endometrium also it rejuvenates the cells and if it's a redundant growth also it reduces the cells therefore helping to homogenize the growth and controlling the hormones involved.

As patient had TORCH test positive, hence to reduce infection and help to conceive Cap. Torchnil was given.

Drugs in Torchnil like Yashtimadhu, Guduchi, Kantakari, Bruhati, Pippali, Usheera, Rasna, Manjishta etc. act as Rasayana, anti-inflammatory activity, promote insulin secretion, blocks protein that is required for virus to replicate. This helped in reduction of infection which prevents from conceiving. Subsequent follicular monitoring and HSG showed normal findings, and the patient conceived naturally after completion of therapy. Continuation of pregnancy with appropriate Ayurvedic and modern antenatal care further supports the safety and effectiveness of the approach.

Thus, this case demonstrates that addressing systemic health, reproductive physiology, and psychological factors simultaneously is essential for successful fertility management.

CONCLUSION

This case report demonstrates that Ayurveda can offer a comprehensive, individualized, and effective approach to the management of infertility associated with Bad Obstetrics history and functional reproductive disorders. By correcting Doṣhic imbalance—particularly Apāna Vāta, purifying Artavavaha srotas, enhancing immunity, and nourishing reproductive tissues, successful conception was achieved without assisted reproductive techniques. Basti karma emerged as a key therapeutic modality in restoring reproductive function. Although this is a single case, the encouraging outcome suggests that Ayurvedic interventions may serve as a valuable complementary option in infertility management. Further controlled clinical studies are warranted to substantiate these findings and establish standardized treatment protocols.

REFERENCES

1. Charaka Samhita with Ayurveda Deepika commentary. Reprint edition :2015. Varanasi Chaukhamba Prakashana;2015, Sharirsthana 4/5.
2. Sushruta, Sushruta Samhita, Nibandha Sangraha commentary of Sri Dalhanacharya edited by Acharya Yadavji Trikamaji, Choukhamba Surabharati Prakashan, Varanasi, 2008, Shareera Sthana, 2nd chapter 35th shloka.
3. Vanishree SK, Chethana Kumari, Sunita Siddesh, Ramesh M. Treating long standing Primary Infertility with Ayurveda - A Case Study. J Ayurveda Integr Med Sci, 2017; 6: 142-149. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21760/jaims.v2i06.10940>
4. Kaviraj Shrigovindadas sen virachit Bhaishajya ratnavali, Siddhiprada Hindiviyakhya by Prof. Siddhinans Mishra, Chaukhamba Surbharti Prakashan, Varanasi, Vatavyadhi Adhikara 151-162.
5. Kaviraj Shrigovindadas sen virachit Bhaishajya ratnavali, Siddhiprada Hindiviyakhya by Prof. Siddhinans Mishra, Chaukhamba Surbharti Prakashan, Varanasi, 9- Arsharoga chikista 203.
6. Kaviraj Shrigovindadas sen virachit Bhaishajya ratnavali, Siddhiprada Hindiviyakhya by Prof.

Siddhinans Mishra, Chaukhamba Surbharti
Prakashan, Varanasi, Adyay 9, pp 329.

7. Charaka Samhita with Ayurveda Deepika commentary. Reprint edition :2015. Varanasi Chaukhamba Prakashana, 2015; Siddhithana 9/50.
8. Vagbhata, Ashthanga Hrudaya, Sarvanga Sundara commentary of Arunadatta and Ayurveda Rsayana commentary of Hemadri, edited by Pandit Hari Sadasivasahastri, Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan, Varanasi, Reprint 2010, Uttarasthana, 34th chapter, 63- 64 Shloka.